

A Pragmatic Study of Deception in Agatha Christie's Novel 'Murder is Easy'

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 17, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Literature texts, Deception, Grecian maxims, Speech acts.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5574561</p>	<p><i>This study is extracted from an MA thesis entitled "Textual Analysis of Deception in Agatha Christie's novel Murder is Easy". The language which is an essential instrument for human communication involves two aspects of discourse: honest and dishonest contributions. Deception is a manifestation of a dishonest contribution. Since it is used commonly, deception is an interesting area to be studied separately. Nevertheless, this concept is not widely investigated from a pragmatic point of view, especially in literary texts. Thus, the present study attempts to examine deception in such a genre of texts pragmatically. Concisely, the present study seeks to answer the question: Which pragmatic aspects are attributed to the deceptive statements in the selected literature texts?. Thus, it aims to identify the maxims that are violated by the characters through their deceptive contributions and the kinds of illocutionary forces that attribute their deceptive utterances. One way to achieve such an aim is to adopt an eclectic model bases on Grice's (1975) cooperative principles, and Searle's (1969) speech act theory for analyzing the selected data.</i></p> <p><i>The finding of the current study shows that the characters violate all of the Grecian maxims through their contributions. It also finds that the deceptive statements attribute to different kinds of illocutionary forces. The study finds that there are no commissive or declarative speech acts in the characters utterances because there are no felicity conditions to achieve such acts in the literary texts.</i></p>

Introduction

Deception is used by the speaker to achieve different purposes. American Heritage Dictionary (1969) elaborates the verb to 'deceive' as that action which "involves falsehood or the deliberate concealment or misrepresentation of truth with intent to lead another into error or to disadvantage" (p.342). From a pragmatic point of view, deception is defined as the act which describes reality as it can be true with the intention to mislead the listener. This can be observed in a case where the speaker presents only one part of a certain situation or employing words out of the context of their real situation (Cutting, 2007). Under this view, deception is seen as an implicature resulted from a single or multiples violations of Grice's (1975) maxims of conversation. In his book 'Expression and Meaning', Searle (1979) asserts that an utterance may have one or more interpretations of meaning. Thus, a deceptive utterance may contain one or more than one meaning. Precisely, a deceptive utterance can be employed by a speaker to provide different illocutionary forces such as deceiving, convincing, persuading, and the like.

Literary texts are those texts that have certain features that differentiated them from others types of texts. Thus, this genre of texts is decorated, fictionally systemized with certain events, and planned to achieve enjoyment, describes a social situation, or imitates certain originated customs. Deception is a common phenomenon in literary texts which is used for several functions such as misleading a character or making a false understanding of the situation of conversation (Cao & Gao, 2007). In Agatha Christie's novel 'Murder is Easy' which is the data of this study, deception is the main theme that is employed to hide the real identity of the killer and to give the plot its climax. The deceptive interaction between the characters of the above novel is characterized by two features: It is designed to quietly imitate the interaction conducted between an investigator and accuser in a criminal case. It is also aimed to describe the deceptive strategies used by the deceptive person in the real everyday life of society.

Pragmatics as a linguistic field, study the intended meaning of the speaker, and what users do with language. Accordingly, the researchers of this study use this approach to investigate the ways by which the characters of the novel deceive or falsify each other in certain exchanges of conversation. More concisely, this study tries to analyze the pragmatic aspects that certain deceptive statement involves. Such kind of search can formulate a practical instrument to develop our capacity to identify a speaker's deceptive attitudes and organizes our contributions to be more informative. To achieve these two aims, the researchers attempt to break down the

selected text pragmatically. This can assign how the characters violate Grecian maxims and discover the reasons behind such violations of the maxims. Besides, it can identify the illocutionary acts that certain deceptive utterance attributes. Investigating the selected data in such a way can entail an accurate interpretation of the concept of deception linguistically.

2. Literature Review on deception

Researchers and authors conduct different studies on the concept of deception. Some of these studies deal with the speaker's reasons behind the use of the phenomenon of deception. Accordingly, Davis (1961) conducts a study on the functions of deception that are employed by deceptive persons. His study concludes that the main reason for using deception is the fear of the consequences that the discovering of the true state involves such as punishment, dismissal, and the like. The above result of Davis's study seems to be a psychological study more than a linguistic study of the concept of deception since it focuses on the speaker's feelings. In front, the current study attempts to discover the pure linguistics aspects of this concept. In another treatment to the concept of deception, Carter & McCarthy (2006) describe the language of deception as that vague language "which deliberately refers to people and things in a non-specific, imprecise way". Their study is confined to the lexical level which deals with the words or the expression that shapes the deceptive contribution. Such a study is suitable for a certain case study such as the brief comments and people reactions. In this regard, the present study attempts to shed light on the strategies employed by the deceptive person in a conversational environment that resembles the interaction of the people in everyday purposeful communication. Icard (2018) writes a thesis about "Lying, Deception and Strategic Omission Definition & Evaluation". His study attempts to identify the criteria that assess a speaker's deceptive contribution. The current study differs from the above study in terms of the approach utilized to inquire the data. To sum up, this study though takes several advantages from the aforementioned studies, but it has its aims, data, and methodology to investigate the concept of deception.

3. Defining Deception

Deception is of considerable complexity to be defined linguistically. Experts such as Baller & Burgoon (1996) argue that deception is the speaker's contribution which makes the partner believes that the false state of something is true. Thus, they regard deception as "a message knowingly transmitted by a sender to foster a false belief or conclusion by the receiver" (p. 205). The message which is mentioned in the previous definition needs certain conditions to be regarded as a deceptive message. The most significant condition in this term is the 'deliberated intention' to deceive the partner. Accordingly, Galasinski (2000) views that deception is not entailed from a mere chance or resulted from unexpected occasions, instead deception is a "deliberated enterprise" (p.15). Deliberateness is the main aspect that motivates scholars to study the concept of deception both, verbally, and non-verbally. Such studies enable the researchers to make boundaries between deception and the mere unintended messages of communication. In this regard, Swol & Braun (2013) clearly define deception as the deliberated acts that consist of crafted messages aimed to make a counterpart in a state of wrong belief.

3.1 Deception from a Pragmatic Perspective

From a pragmatic point of view, deception is regarded as an exception from the traditional norms of discourse. Mey (1993) argues that the aim of using language is to purposely communicate, hence, the speaker pays an effort to make his contribution understandable and reflects no misleading impression on the part of the listener. Accordingly, he says that "communication is not a matter of logic or truth, but of cooperation; not of what I say, but of what I can say, given the circumstances" (p. 57). Intentionality which is a pragmatic aspect is conventionally regarded as a condition in assigning certain statements as a deceptive statements. In this regard, Carson (2010) defines deception as "intentionally causing someone to have a false belief that the deceiver believes to be false" (p. 47). Thus, there is a pragmatic condition to regard a certain utterance as a deceptive one or not. This condition is that the speaker should intentionally mislead the partner or intentionally creates a false belief in his mind.

Moreover, Mey (1993) asserts that the speaker may ignore the maxims of conversation to achieve a deliberate omission or misleading the counterpart. Isabel (2013) views deception as an 'act' of deceiving the listener. Identifying the concept of deception as an act is also discussed by Walter (2000) who claims that the concept of deception can be identified due to certain acts it involves. Thus, he states that deception can represent an act of prevaricating, fabricating, misleading, inventing, hedge, fib, or lie. (p. 6). Oswald (2014) defines deception as the phenomenon of a perlocutionary act where it is used to attain a certain aim. From the above explanation, it can be argued that the phenomenon of deception is a pragmatic strategy employed by the user of the language to achieve certain goals in purposeful communication.

3. 2 Linguistic Features of Deception

Studies that are conducted on the phenomena of deception conclude that the deceivers are untrusted with their selves. Consequently, their behaviors and feeling appear unorganized. This state of instability affects the language that they use through their storytelling. Linguists state several features that frequently attribute to a deceptive statement. Picornel (2013) mentions four linguistic cues that can shape the deceptive statement. These cues are the type of pronoun, signs of cognitive complexity, the number of words of the sentence, and the emotional words that accompanied the deceptive contribution.

Type of pronoun in a certain statement is frequently used to relate the responsibility of the action of that statement with its subject. In the truth cases, the speaker relates the responsibility of something to himself. Deceivers, on the contrary, attempt to get rid of the responsibility of an action that they perform. Missing self-personal pronouns is one of the strategies employed by deceptive persons. In such a case the statement which is produced by the deceptive person seems empty of the self-pronouns such as 'I', 'we', 'me', 'ourselves', and 'myself'. Instead, the deceptive speaker tends to use the passive voice version of the statement to describe the action of his statement (Zimmer, 2010).

Lack of sufficient experience about a certain event is directly reflected in the language which the deceiver uses in an interaction. In these terms, the deceptive person produces limited details about the event in which he is engaged. Moreover, the deceiver seems to have no clear image about the process that leads to the current event. Such issues can increase the loading on the mind of the deceiver and conclude in an unorganized storytelling for the events of the interaction. Milene & Bull (2008) state that the deceiver tends to provide an alternative version of the real fact to be more believable or readjusts their claims. Such troubles of storytelling lead to a considerable cognitive complexity on the part of the deceiver (DePaulo, 1985).

Word quantity is another aspect that is utilized by the investigators to identify the deceptive statement. Comparing with the true storyteller, deceivers provide short verbal responses through the description of an event. This strategy is employed by the deceivers because he thinks that the long contribution may involve signs of false information and that can be caught or observed by an investigator. Consequently, the deceptive person tends to say as little as possible about the event of the interaction.

De Paulo (1985) states that deceptive person is frequently employed emotion words to affect his partner. In this regard, there are two types of emotion words: words of negative emotion, and exclusive words. Words of negative emotion such as (anger, hate) are used to send a message to the partner that the speaker is offended. This strategy is used by the deceiver to motivate the partner to close the discussion. Exclusive words such as (but, without) are used to provide misinforming the partner.

It should mention that the genre is an aspect that can be considered by the investigators to identify the deceptive statement. In this term, several researchers argue that men are more deceiving than women. De Paulo (1985) comments on such claims. He views that it is difficult to assign a certain genre to be more deceptive than another. Instead, he argues that the conversation between men-men or women-women can provide another complexity to scale the average of deception between the two genres.

3. 3 Purposes of Deception

Pragmatically speaking, deception has two major types of functions: positive functions, and negative functions. Positive functions of deception are expressed by the unintentional deception which is used to develop the 'flexibility of the communication'. In such a case the speaker tends to use expressions that soften the atmospheres of the interaction. This function of deception is employed by the speaker in a polite environment. In addition, deception can be used to motivate the 'persuasiveness of communication'. Schaff (1979) views that truth storytelling tends to be sharp and its communication appears too pale. In such a case deception is used to moisturize the sharpness of the situation. Another positive function of deception is that which is used by the speaker to avoid conflict and psychological injury (Akman, 1995).

Negative purposes of deception are very broad where they range from misleading, fabricating, manipulating the listener, to all the purposes of concealment. Kinds of negative purposes of deception are very familiar in everyday communication and shape several types of discourse such as political, social, international discourse, and the likes. Akman (1995) summarizes the functions of deception in three majors motivations: to gain the admiration of the counterpart, to get rid of non-preferable social discussion, and to win power which is used for controlling the others (p.63). De Paulo (1985) views that deception can be described as negative or positive due to the type of discourse in which it is used. In this regard, political discourse tends to use negative deception more than the other kinds of discourse (van Dike, 2002).

3.4 Forms of Deception

Several attempts are conducted by scholars to categorize the forms of deception. most of these studies are agreed that deception can be categorized into Silent deception, distortion of information, generalization, manipulating the picture of the event, and abandonment from a human being (Peterson, 2010).

Silent deception is a very familiar form of deception. in this kind of deception, the deceiver deliberately covers the true state of something but does not produce false information instead. It is called silent because the deceiver shows no deceptive signs. In such a case the deceiver tends to avoid any direct participation in the process of communication. Rejection to conduct a communication is not a marker for deception, but it entails that the speaker hides something about the case (De Paulo, 1985).

Distortion of the information is also called intentional deception. in this kind of deception, the speaker hides the true state of something and provides a false contribution to mislead his partner. It is called distortion because the speaker twists the fact of a certain case by providing an alternative version of the true cause. Deceiver of this kind of deception, pay attention to both, the structure, and the content of his statement (Picornel, 2003).

Generalized deception is another type of deception in which the deceiver uses broad expression to avoid the direct answer to the listener's question. Expressions that are used in such kind of deception can be exemplified by (frequently, always, somebody, generally) (Peterson, 2010).

Another kind of deception is manipulating the picture of the event. In this kind, the deceiver tries to manipulate the natural occurrence of the true state of something. The marker of the deceptive statement, in this case, is the lack of details that the speaker provides through his storytelling of the case (De Paolo, 2003).

In some cases, the deceiver dissociates himself from the occurrence of the event. This kind of deception is called abandonment by a human being. In this term, the deceiver uses expressions such as (that man, that individual, he, they).

3.5 Related Concept of Deception

In fact, deception is only one form from several concepts of concealment. Generally, these concepts share one universal meaning of misleading, but they differ mainly from each other if they are regarded from a linguistic standpoint. Regardless of their semantic nature, the researchers in this study attempt to shed light on these concepts from a pragmatic point of view.

1. Falsification: A process in which the truth information is changed to falsify the partner.
2. Misdirection: In which the speaker tells true information, but in a way that the partner cannot verify them.
3. Minimization: This is the reduction of the significance that the true information involves.
4. Equivocation: Is the deliberate use of ambiguous language through describing something.
5. Prevarication: A way of storytelling in which the speaker avoids the direct answer to the listener's question.
6. Exaggeration: A way of making something more significant, better, or vice versa.
7. Half-truth: In which the speaker tells true information, but incompletely.

3.6 Deception in the Literary Texts

Literary texts are those texts that are decorated, fictionally organized, and planned to be read. Literary texts especially novels are written to tackle certain issues that the writer thinks to have a significance for his readers. The issues that are discussed in the novels are called 'themes'. The theme is the real face of the fiction event that the plot of the novel moves around. Deception is a very familiar theme in the novels. It is organized in positive or negative function due to the main tendency of that literary work. In Agatha Christie's novel '*murder is easy*', deception is used to achieve both, positive and negative functions, though the negative version is the dominant one.

4. Cooperative Principles

Grice (1975) states that the speaker is assumed to be cooperative through an exchange of conversation. The norms that govern the speaker to be truthful are called cooperative principles. The main idea in the cooperative principles is that "make your conversational contribution such as required, at the stage at which it occurs, by the accepted purpose or direction of the talk's exchange in which you are engaged" (p.30). For a further explanation, the founder of the cooperative principle (also called maxims of conversation) categorizes them into four maxims: maxim of quantity, the maxim of quality, the maxim of manner, and maxim of relevance.

In maxim of quantity Grice (1975) states two sub-maxims: Make your contribution as informative as possible, and do not make your participation more than is required.

In maxim of quality, the speaker should not say what he believes to be false, and should not say what you have not adequate evidence.

In maxim of manner, the speaker should avoid ambiguous expressions, avoid obscurity, should be brief, and orderly.

In maxim of relevance, the speaker should provide information that is relevant to the main topic of the exchange. Grice (1975) states that a speaker is liable to deceive his partner when he violates certain maxim, for example, the violation of the maxim of quality entails either deception or lying (p. 46).

5. Speech Acts and Deception

Speech acts theory is the most important aspect in the field of pragmatics. It is found by Austin (1958) and developed by Searle (1969). One of the familiar assumptions in the theory of speech acts is that the speaker intends certain meaning when he utters certain utterances. Deceiving is an act in which the speaker provides false information about something. A deceptive utterance may attribute an act of assertion "a deception is an act of insincere assertion" (Oswald, 2014, p.6). It can be also a speech act of persuading, convincing, misleading, and so on. Searle's speech acts as it has various versions of illocutionary forces can be regarded as a reasonable method to analyze the deceptive utterances within the literary genre of texts.

5.1 Searle's Categorization of Speech Acts

An interesting categorization of illocutionary acts is presented by Searle (1969). Archer (1979) states that the classification of illocutionary acts suggested by Searle (1969) is a reasonable way to draw boundaries

between the speaker's utterances. Searle classifies speech acts into five major types of acts. His classification is based on what can the speakers do with language. These five types of illocutionary acts are classified due to "their fit to the world, psychological state, and above all the purpose of the illocution, illocutionary point" (Suleiman, 2016, p.292). The general five types of illocutionary acts involve various rooms of sub-categories of illocutionary acts systemized due to the forces they contain. For such reasons, the researchers of this study think that Searle's (1969) classification of speech acts is a consistent and applicable method to investigate the literary texts selected for this study. The five major types of speech acts are:

1. Representatives: Also called (assertive) the speaker in such acts expresses his thoughts of truthfulness about what he utters. The purpose of representatives should express "word-to-world fit" (Mey, 1993, p.131). This means that certain utterance is interpreted to fit the speaker belief. Examples of representatives are asserting, describing, suggesting, boasting, and claiming.
2. Commissives: Speech acts in which the speaker commits himself to do something in the future. In such kinds of acts, the speaker is responsible to fit the world into the words. An example of speech acts of commissives is promising.
3. Directives: In the directives speech act the speaker wants to get the listener to do something. Illocutionary acts of ordering, requesting, entertaining are examples of such categories of speech acts.
4. Expressives: in expressive speech acts the speaker reflects a certain psychological state towards the listener. Speech acts such as thanking, apologizing are examples of such speech acts.
5. Declarative: in such kinds of speech acts the state of something is changed from the current situation to another, as in the case of declaring war or declaring marriage. The success of such speech acts requires the speaker to have certain institutionalization such as the empire, king, president, chief, and the likes. Deception as a linguistic phenomenon can be expressed by speech acts of representatives, commissives, and expressive. In front, deception is rarely expressed by speech acts of declarative, and directives, since they required special felicity conditions to be succeeded.

6. Methodology

The purpose of this study is to investigate the concept of deception from a pragmatic standpoint. Deception in this regard is expressed by the violations of the four maxims of conversation and the illocutionary acts that certain deceptive utterance involves. The methodology of this study is composed of the data collection, genre, form, length, theme, and model of analysis for the data selected.

6.1 Data collection

The data of this study is extracted from a well-known literary work which is the novel '*Murder is Easy*'. It is one of Agatha Christie's detective works. To avoid redundancy the issue of representativeness is taken into consideration through the collection of the data. Thus, four texts are selected in readjustment with the four maxims of conversation. Each text reflects certain maxim violations and a certain form of deception.

6.2 Genre

The data of the present study is literary text, namely a novel entitled "*Murder is Easy*". The language of this work is systemized to describe the phenomenon of deception in a fictional plot and a countryside setting.

6.3 Form

All the selected texts are written texts in conversational forms conducted between two or three characters of the above novel. There is no visual scene or video recorded to be analyzed in this study.

6.4 Theme

The main theme of the selected texts is the investigation of the killer of several victims. In this regard, the killer violates different maxims of conversation to deceive his listeners. Moreover, the killer uses different deceptive utterances that associate with different illocutionary forces. For this reason, the researchers of the current study think that it is reasonable to investigate such a theme pragmatically to find an appropriate interpretation for the concept of deception in the literary text.

6.5 Model of analysis

The model of analysis of the current study is an eclectic model. This eclectic model is based on the pragmatic aspects illustrated in section four and section five. Thus, it is based on Gricean (1975) theory of cooperative principles, and Searle's (1969) theory of speech acts theory. Gricean cooperative principle is expressed by the violations of the four maxims of conversation. In this regard, the characters violate the maxims of conversation for several purposes such as deceiving, misleading, convincing, etc. All of the four maxims quantity, quality, manner, and relevance that are violated by the characters are considered in this study. Speech acts theory is expressed by the major categories and their sub-categories such as assertion, questioning, claiming, etc. The declarative, and directives speech acts are not considered in this study because of the nature of the selected texts, and the socially equal status of the characters within the texts of the selected data of this study. Figure (1) below summarizes the mechanism of this model:

Figure 1

The Theoretical Framework of the Current Study

7. Data Analysis

7.1

Text 1

*Luck "I am down here to inquire into the circumstances of the death of that poor girl, Amy Gibbs."
Miss Waynfleete said, "You mean you have been sent down by the police?"
"Oh, no, I'm not a plain-clothes dick." He added, with a slightly humorous inflection, "I'm afraid I'm that well-known character in fiction, the private investigator."*

6.1.1 Violation of Maxims

The above text involves is a conversation between two characters in a form of question and answer. The two characters are Waynfleete (an accuser), and Luck (an investigator). Accordingly, Miss Waynfleete asks Luck who investigates the several deaths in the town "You mean you have been sent down by the police?". This question is syntactically well organized, and clear to be understood by the listener. Nevertheless, Luck intentionally negates his identity when he says "Oh, no, I'm not a plain-clothes dick." Thus, he says to his partner something which he knows is false. By this contribution, Luck is untruthful and purposely deceives his interlocutor. Doing so, Luck violates the maxim of quality.

As it is mentioned in section four of this study, the speaker violates a certain maxim for a certain reason. Grice (1975) states that the flouting of the maxim of quality is called deceiving. Moreover, Khosravizadeh, & Sadehvandi, (2011) view that the violation of the maxim of quality is more deceitful than any other maxims violations. Correspondingly, Luck intentionally violates the quality maxim to mislead or deceive Waynfleete about his real identity. He satisfies her that he is a fiction writer nothing more.

7.1.2 Speech Acts Attribute this Text

This text involves deceptive utterances formulated by the writer to reflects five types of illocutionary forces. Each type belongs to a certain category of Sealer's (1969) speech act theory. Thus, the utterance "I am down here to inquire into the circumstances of the death of that poor girl Amy Gibbs" involves a speech act of 'explaining'. Explaining is to tell somebody about an unknown case to be understood. Explaining is a sub-category that belongs to the representative speech acts in sealer's (1969) classification.

In parallel line with the act of explaining mentioned so far, Waynfleete asks Luck "You mean you have been sent down by the police?". This utterance involves a speech act of 'questioning'. Questioning is an act by which the speaker raises a question to gain information about the nature of something. The utterance which attributes to a speech act of questioning has a special linguistic formation. Thus, it should be opened with an instrument of a question, rise-fall intonation, and closed with a question mark.

In an answer to the above question, Luck deceptively says "Oh, no, I am not a plainclothes dick". This utterance attributes a speech act of 'negating'. Negating is an act that is utilized to deny the occurrence or performance of something. Negation itself is a familiar strategy employed by deceptive people to conceal the partner, especially in the sudden question state.

The statement "I am not a plainclothes dick" is moreover, involves a speech act of 'asserting'. Asserting is a very familiar speech act that accompanies the concept of deception. This fact is stated by Oswald(2014) who views that "a deception is an act of insincere assertion". Asserting is not always assure a true proposition. Thus, the deceptive persons utilize such anact to persuade an addressee about their deceptive claim.

Luck's utterance "*I'm afraid I'm that well-known character in fiction, the private investigator*" associates a 'stating panic' speech act. Stating panic is an act in which the speaker appears unable to think correctly or loses his smooth way of interaction. Panic in such a case employed by the investigator to discover a deceptive statement.

7.2

Text 2

"You seem to have a lot of deaths here," said Luke lightly.

Lord Easterfield bridled immediately. "Not at all. One of the healthiest places in England. Can't count accidents. They may happen to anyone."

But Bridget Conway said thoughtfully, "As a matter of fact, Gordon, there have been a lot of deaths in the last year. They're always having funerals."

"Nonsense, my dear."

Luke said, "Was Doctor Humbleby's death an accident too?"

Lord Easterfield shook his head. "Oh, no," he said. "Humbleby died of acute septicemia. Just like a doctor. Scratched his finger with a rusty nail or something, paid no attention to it, and it turned septic. He was dead in three days."

"Doctors are rather like that," said Bridget. "And of course they're very liable to infection, I suppose, if they don't take care. It was sad though. His wife was broken-hearted."

"No good of rebelling against the will of Providence," said Lord Easterfield easily.

7.2.1 Violation of Maxims

The maxim which is violated in this conversation is the manner maxim. It is violated two times through the interaction of the characters. The character who is responsible for this violation is Easterfield. In this text, Luck raises a semi-question when he asks Easterfield "*You seem to have a lot of deaths here*". Easterfield is expected to assure the phenomena of the various deaths simultaneously, instead, he says "*One of the healthiest places in England. Can't count accidents*". According to the maxim of manner, the speaker should be brief, informative, clear, and confident. Correspondingly, Easterfield's answer violates these features all in one.

The second violation of the maxim of manner in this text can be observed in the conversation between Bridget and Easterfield. Bridget says "*As a matter of fact, Gordon, there have been a lot of deaths in the last year*", and Easterfield replies "*nonsense*". Saying "*Nonsense*", Easterfield violates the manner's sub-maxim of clarity. Clarity means that the speaker selects the best way for his storytelling and "that no other way of saying the same thing would be significantly clearer" (Birner, 2013, p.58).

In terms of the purposes of violating the maxim of manner, Dörnyei (2005) argues that the maxim of manner is violated in a certain contribution to 'communicate self-interest'. Accordingly, Easterfield utilizes the expression of "*nonsense*" to assure that "*Humbleby died of acute septicemia. Just like a doctor*" and to conceal any other reasons behind the case.

7.2.2 Speech Acts Attribute this Text

The phenomenon of deception is grown in an ambiguous situation. An ambiguous situation can cause surprising effects on an addressee. Consequently, the ambiguous deaths in the town motivate Luck to ask Easterfield "*You seem to have a lot of deaths here*". This utterance involves a speech act of 'stating surprise'. Stating surprise is the act by which a speaker expresses his surprise about the unexpected happening of something. This kind of speech act is a sub-category of the expressive speech acts in Searle's (1969) categorization.

In response to Luck's statement mentioned above, Easterfield says "*Not at all. One of the healthiest places in England. Can't count accident*". This utterance involves a speech act of 'stating opinion'. In this kind of speech act, the speaker tells the listener his point of view about something regardless of the proposition's truthfulness. Accordingly, Easterfield (though deceptive) tells Luck his opinion about the recent events of the deaths in the town.

Easterfield's utterance "*Nonsense, my dear*" attributes a speech act of 'arguing'. Arguing speech act reflects the opposite attitude of the speaker toward something. Arguing in this text is used by Easterfield as an opposition to Bridget's contribution "*there have a lot of deaths in the last years. They're always having a funeral*".

Moreover, Bridget's utterance "*And of course they're very liable to infection, I suppose if they don't care. It was though*" associates a speech act of 'predicting'. In predicting a speech act, the speaker expects the occurrence of something based on some given information. In this utterance, Bridget expects the consequences that may affect the doctors if they don't care their selves.

Easterfield's utterance "*Humbleby died of acute septicemia. Just like a doctor. Scratched his finger with a rusty nail or something, paid no attention to it, and it turned septic. He was dead in three days*" attributes a speech act of 'reporting'. Reporting is a sub-category of the representatives speech acts in Searle's classification of speech act. One notable feature of this speech act is that the utterance which carries it, tends to be too long since it gives a decent account to something.

Alongside the above text, the speaker Easterfield employs utterances that reflect his opinion, negating, or convincing in a reporting way. If we check such utterances we conclude that all of them are employed to give rise to the speaker's deceptive statements.

7.3

Text 3

Bridget said, "How long have you known that - that Gordon was the killer, Miss Waynflete?"

Miss Waynflete sighed. "That is a difficult question to answer, my dear. I suppose that I have been quite sure in my inmost heart, for some time. But I did my best not to recognize that belief. You see, I didn't want to believe it and so I pretended to myself that it was a wicked and monstrous idea on my part."

Luke said bluntly, "Have you never been afraid for yourself?"

Miss Waynflete considered. "You mean that if Gordon had suspected that I knew, he would have found some means of getting rid of me?"

"Yes." Miss Waynflete said gently, "I have, of course, been alive to that possibility. I tried to be careful of myself. But I do not think that Gordon would have considered me a real menace."

"Why?"

Miss Waynflete flushed a little. "I don't think that Gordon would ever believe that I would do anything to - to bring him into danger."

Luke said abruptly, "You went as far, didn't you, as to warn him?"

7.3.1 Violation of Maxims

This text involves an evident violation to the quantity maxim. The character who violates this maxim is Waynflete. This violation is observed through the interaction between Bridget and Waynflete. Thus, Bridget asks Waynflete "*How long have you know that – that Gorden was the killer miss Waynflete?*". Waynflete replies "*that is a difficult question to answer, my dear, I suppose that I have been quite sure in my inmost heart, for some time*". This contribution involves a violation of the maxim of quantity. According to the maxim of quantity, the speaker should provide sufficient information no much more. On contrary, Waynflete produces too much uninformative information.

According to Khosravizadeh & Sadehvandi (2011), the maxim of quantity is violated by the speaker to achieve two purposes: It is violated when the speaker attempts to deny the unpredicted question. It is also violated when the speaker avoids a direct question through a certain discussion. In this text, Waynflete violates the quantity maxim to deny any unpredicted question which may be raised by Bridget. She also attempts to close the debate about the death of Amy which may involve bad consequences toward her. To sum up, the maxim of quantity is violated by Waynflete to mislead Bridget and Luck from discovering the real identity of the killer. Thus, she presupposes them that Gorden is the killer of Amy.

7.3.2 Speech Acts Attribute this Text

This text is opened with a question raised by Bridget about certain historical distance "*How long have you known that-that Gorden was the killer*". This utterance attributes a speech act of 'stating'. In stating act, the speaker states a certain distance of place, time or it is used to state the quantity of something. This kind of act is a sub-category of the representatives speech acts in Searle's classification of speech acts. Stating is a scientific term that governs the listener to carefully state the events that accompanied the occurrence of the case. It is worthy to mention that the act of stating is improper to the deceptive utterances thus, it is labeled here to Bridget because she is a frank character along the plot of the novel..

In a dodging strategy from Bridget's question, Waynflete says "*That is a difficult question to answer, my dear. I suppose that I have been quite sure in my inmost heart, for some time*". This utterance involves an illocutionary act of 'convincing'. Convincing is to provide sequenced information about something to persuade the listener. Accordingly, Waynflete attempt to convince Bridget that she has irresponsibility for Amy's murder.

Waynflete's utterance "*I have, of course, been alive to that possibility. I tried to be careful of myself*" involves a speech act of 'stating fear'. Stating fear belongs to the expressives speech acts in Searle's categorization. In stating fear the speaker describes his feeling of a scare from the occurrence of a certain event.

Thus, Waynflete describes her feeling of a scare from Gordon if he knows that she inform the police about Amy's death.

As he is surprised by Waynflete's fear, Luck suggests an exclamation by the utterance "why". The expression of 'why' is linguistically used to ask about the cause and effect. Pragmatically speaking, this expression can be used to ask about an unusual occurrence of something. In this text, the expression of "why" involves a speech act of 'sating doubt'. It is a sub-category of the expressives speech acts in which an individual expresses his doubt toward something. In this text, the utterance "why" is employed by Luck to express his doubt about Waynflete's state.

Luck's statement "You went as far, didn't you, as to warn him" attributes an illocutionary act of 'suggesting'. Suggesting is to give someone your opinion or an advise about something. In this text, Luck suggests Waynflete that "You went as far, didn't you, as to warn him?" if Gordon troubles her.

7.4

Text 4

"Quite so. This is a private conversation. We are merely speaking about what we think and suspect. We suspect Amy Gibbs was murdered. Who do we think murdered her?"

Miss Waynflete shook her head. She was looking very troubled. Luke said, watching her, "Who had reason to murder her?"

Miss Waynflete said slowly, "She had had a quarrel, I believe, with her young man at the garage, Jim Harvey - a most steady, superior young man. I know one reads in the papers of young men attacking their sweethearts, and dreadful things like that, but I really can't believe that Jim would do such a thing." Luke nodded.

7.4.1 Violation of Maxim

The maxim which is violated in this text is the relevance maxim. The character who violates this maxim is Waynflete. According to the maxim of relevance the speaker should design his contribution as "to be relevant" to the main point of the interaction in which the speaker is involved (Grice, 1975, p. 46). Thus, the speaker's contribution should be directly related to the purpose of the interaction. In contrary to this norm, Waynflete produces information that is unrelated to Luck's question. In an analytical callout, Luck asks Waynflete a direct question "Who do we think murdered her?", and Waynflete intentionally avoids the direct answer, and thus, she says "Who had reason to murder her?". Luck expects that she will say that Jim or somebody else is the killer. Consequently, Luck gains nothing new about the name of the killer.

It is worthy to say that, the answer to a question with a question is one of the linguistic features that recognize the deceptive statement (Susan, 1996). Moreover, Khosravizadeh & Sadehvandi (2011) argue that one of the reasons behind flouting the maxim of relevance is to shift the direction of the discussion between the participants. In this text, Waynflete violates the relevance maxim to shift the direction of the discussion toward Jim to be the killer of Amy.

7.4.2 Speech Acts Attribute this Text

This text attributes four sub-categories of speech acts. The text is opened with Luck's contribution "This is a private conversation", then he continues that "We suspect Amy Gibbs was murdered". His contribution is systemized to perform a speech act of 'informing'. Informing speech act is to tell an addressee something to be the case. Informing is different from the speech act of reporting in that reporting is a result of a certain observation of something. Thus, reporting is more scientific and longer than the act of informing. Informing is specified to the limited information that can be part of the reporting act. As a speech act informing is a sub-category of the representatives speech acts.

Luck's utterance "who do we think murdered her?" attributes also a speech act of 'encouraging'. In this kind of speech acts the speaker motivates his addressee to do something. It is used in a situation where the speaker observes a hesitation that controls the behavior of his addressee. The plural pronoun of 'we' is employed to share the responsibility with the addressee.

Waynflete's statement "Who had reason to murder her?" attributes an illocutionary act of 'reasoning'. In the reasoning speech act, the speaker investigates the logical reasons behind the occurrence of something. Reasoning speech act represents an expressive speech act in Searle's categorization. In this text, the reasoning is employed deceptively by Waynflete to avoid the accusation of Amy's murder.

The writer's statement "She was looking very trouble" which describes Waynflete's state attributes a speech act of 'stating confusion'. Confusion is a psychological state in which an individual's behavior appears uncontrolled or random. Stating confusion is a speech act that belongs to the expressive speech act in Searle's classification. Accordingly, Waynflete appears "very trouble" when she faces certain facts which may lead to an accusation against her in Amy's murder. Confusion itself is a psychological sign for identifying a deceptive person (De Paulo, 2003).

Waynflete's utterance "*She quarreled, I believe, with her young man at the garage, Jim Harvey- a most steady, superior young man*" involves a speech act of 'justifying'. Thus, Waynflete justifies her claim that somebody kills Amy by this statement. It should mention here that, deceptive people tend to use feeble justifications for their statements.

8. Statistical Analysis of the Findings

The aforementioned analysis of the data can be better understood by adopting a numerical account of its findings. This account is statistically indexed into three tables. The first table is dedicated to the violations of the Grecian maxims by the characters. Thus, it demonstrates the maxim which is violated, the character who violates the maxim, and the reasons behind that violation. The second table illustrates the majors' kinds of speech acts and their subcategories that attribute the deceptive statements. In the third table, the researchers mathematically calculate the **frequencies and percentages of speech acts in the deceptive utterances**.

Table 1

Classification of the Violations of Maxims, the Characters who Violate the Maxims, and the Reasons behind the Violations in the Selected Texts

Data No	The Violated Maxim	Character	Reason for Violation the Maxim
Text 1	Quality	Luck	Deceiving the counterpart
Text 2	Manner	Easterfield	Communicating a self-interest
Text 3	Quality	MissWaynflete	Avoidance of a direct answer
Text 4	Relevance	MissWaynflete	Shifting the topic of interaction

Note : The above table describes only the single violations of the maxims in the selected texts, but that does not mean that there are no multiples violations of the maxims in the selected texts. The multiple violations that need more explanation are mentioned in the theses from which this article is extracted.

Table 2

Classification of the Majors Kinds of Speech Acts and their Subcategories that Attribute the Deceptive Utterances in the Selected Texts

Data No	Representative speech acts	Expressives speech acts	Directives speech acts
Text 1	Explaining, negating, asserting	Stating panic	Questioning
Text 2	Stating opinion, arguing, predicting, reporting	Stating surprise	
Text 3	Stating, convincing	Stating fear, stating doubt	Suggesting
Text 4	Informing, justifying	Reasoning, confusing	Encouraging

Note : The selected texts have no commissives or declarative speech acts. Such kinds of speech acts need special kinds of felicity conditions that are not available in the literary texts especially in the novel "*Murder is Easy*" which reflects an equal status of its characters.

Table 3

Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Acts in the Deceptive Utterances.

Types of speech acts	frequency	percentage
Representatives	11	55%
Expressives	6	30%
Directives	3	15%
Commissives	0	0%
Declaratives	0	0%

Note: The calculation of the speech acts in the above table is accounted according to the sub-categories that a certain category of speech acts involves. Thus, the selected texts of this study involve 11 sub-categories of the representatives speech acts, six sub-categories of the expressives speech acts, and three sub-categories of the directives speech acts.

9. Conclusion

Based on the findings and the statistical analysis of the data, the current study comes up with the following conclusions.

1. The findings of the current study verify the claim that deception involved in Agatha Christies novel 'Murder is Easy' can be interpreted accurately by a pragmatic consideration for its appearance in the character's contributions.
2. As far as violations of maxims are concerned, the findings and the statistical analysis show that the concept of deception can result from the violation of each one of the Grecian maxims of conversation. The findings show also that there are several purposes for violating the maxims but the reasons for deceiving and misleading are the prominent reasons behind such violations.
3. The findings of the current study show that deception can be expressed by different kinds of speech acts. The statistical analysis of the findings shows also that certain speech acts such as representatives are more appropriate to the literary texts than the others kinds of speech acts. Thus, in the four selected texts, the highest percentage is dedicated to the representatives speech acts that occupy 55% of the deceptive utterances. The statistical analysis shows that expressive speech acts occupy 30% of the deceptive utterances, whereas the directives speech acts compose 15% of the illocutionary forces involved in the deceptive utterances. The study shows that commissives and declarative speech acts are not employed by the characters through their interaction, because such acts need special felicity conditions and institutional position to be succeeded.
4. The findings of the current study result that the concept of deception can be expressed by multiples strategies such as violations of maxims and intended meanings that can be deceptively interpreted by an addressee. For this reason, it is better to study the concept of deception pragmatically to break it down to its real atoms.

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